

Working Motivation Factors Affecting Job Performance Effectiveness

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Abstract—The purpose of this paper was to study motivation factors affecting job performance effectiveness. This paper drew upon data collected from an Internal Audit Staffs of Internal Audit Line of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited. Statistics used included frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation, t-test, and one-way ANOVA test. The finding revealed that the majority of the respondents were female of 46 years of age and over, married and live together, hold a bachelor degree, with an average monthly income over 70,001 Baht. The majority of respondents had over 15 years of work experience. They generally had high working motivation as well as high job performance effectiveness.

The hypotheses testing disclosed that employees with different working status had different level of job performance effectiveness at a 0.01 level of significance. Working motivation factors had an effect on job performance in the same direction with high level. Individual working motivation included working completion, reorganization, working progression, working characteristic, opportunity, responsibility, management policy, supervision, relationship with their superior, relationship with co-worker, working position, working stability, safety, privacy, working conditions, and payment. All of these factors related to job performance effectiveness in the same direction with medium level.

Keywords—Internal Audit Staffs, Job Performance Effectiveness, Working Motivation.

I. INTRODUCTION

HUMAN Resources or employees are the most significant assets for an organization because they are the key components to empower the organization to obtain goals. Successful organizational skills always come from the effectiveness of working performance of its assets. If the employees have a shortage of work efficiency, ability, motivation and organization engagement, this will cause some work issues. For example, non-functional work performance: frequency of work relocation, high rate of resignation and new employees; all these issues, will make the organization fail. On the other hand, if the organization has better-qualified assets who are willing to work and love what they do then there will be motivation in the workplace. Hence, motivation in the workplace can come from individuals' personality. For instance, enthusiastic, self-willingness, life progress and positive work attitudes which may come from the liking of the task assignment, matching between task and abilities, good co-workers, and positive attitude with an organization. All of the

factors that were mentioned above may affect the employees' willingness to work better and become more successful in their position [1].

At the present time, Internal Audit Staffs of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited are controlled by four different outsources which include the Bank of Thailand, the Office of the Securities and Exchange Commission, the Office of the Auditor General of Thailand, and the State Enterprise Policy Office. These restrictions have an effect on the workload that is given to the internal audit staffs. The findings show that when an employee is overloaded with work. The results are not good. The employee will be unable to complete their work in a timely manner and/ or produce inadequate results.

Hence, motivation in the workplace for Internal Audit Staffs of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited is very important to drive all employees to be able to work and love their organization, as well as work effectively to reach their goals. The results from this study will be used to benefit employees by better equipping them to maintain the same level of skill in other organizations.

II. METHODOLOGY

The objectives of this study were: 1) Compare the effectiveness of working performance of Internal Audit Staffs of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited by classifying the staffs' personal basic factors 2) Study the relationship between working motivation and effectiveness in the work place of Internal Audit Staffs of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited.

The Research Hypotheses were: 1) the Internal Audit Staffs of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited whose different personal basic factors will have a different effect on their working performance 2) Working motivation would relate to the effectiveness in the work place of Internal Audit Staffs of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited.

The theory of working motivation, 'Two-factor Theory', Herzberg [2] and the study of the factors affecting work performance effectiveness, shows the 6 levels of personal basic factors [3].

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Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

The population of this study was 256 Internal Audit Staff of Internal Audit Line of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited from Human Resources Department in February 2011. The random sample for this study consisted of 115 Internal Audit Staffs of Internal Audit Line of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited. In this study a *stratified random sampling* method was used to portion the samples of internal audit staffs from each department as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
 NUMBER OF SAMPLE

Department	Proportional Stratified Random Sampling	Number of sampling (set)
1 Internal Audit Line	6(155/256)	4
2 Internal Audit Group	2(155/256)	1
3 Head office Internal Audit Line Section	37(155/256)	22
4 Medium and Large Enterprise Audit Section	33(155/256)	19
5 Metropolitan area network Audit Section	32(155/256)	19
6 Regional Network Audit Section	73(155/256)	45
7 Information Technology Audit Section	33(155/256)	20
8 Credit Review Audit Section	40(155/256)	25
Total	256	155

Internal Audit Staffs of Internal Audit Line of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited was selected through random drawing.

III. FINDINGS

The results of this study revealed that the majority of the respondents are females of 46 years of age and over, married/co-habitation status, bachelor degree holder, monthly income over 70,001 baht and have over 15 years of work experience, generally have high working motivation and high effectiveness in working performance.

The hypothesis testing disclosed that staffs with different ranking had different working effective and flexibility at the statistical significance at 0.01. Overall working motivation relates with working effectiveness in the same high level direction. Individual aspects of working motivation include working completion, reorganization, working progression, working characteristic, opportunity, responsibility, policy and management, supervision, relationship with leader, relationship with co-worker, working position, working stability and safety, privacy, working conditions, and payment show in the same medium level direction of the statistical significance at 0.01.

IV. DISCUSSION

The comparative analysis of the effectiveness of working performance of Internal Audit Staffs of Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited shows the status has an effect on effectiveness and flexibility. The analysis represents the statistical significance at 0.01. The study can be explain in the way of single status staffs, marriage/ co-habitation status staffs having higher working effectiveness than widow, divorce, and separate status. This may be because they can work extra hours and are dedicated. The study of Hathairat Tansuwan [4] discovered factors of organizational culture, organizational loyalty and organizational environment affecting work effectiveness of head office staff at Industrial Estate Authority of Thailand. It was found that different marriage statuses have a change on the ability in working effectiveness at the statistical significance 0.05.

The overall working motivation and Individual aspects of at working motivation are related with working effectiveness. The individual aspects of working motivation include working completion, re- organization, working progression, working characteristic, opportunity, responsibility, policy and management, supervision, relationship with leader, relationship with co-worker, work position, working stability and safety, privacy, working conditions, and payments related with the working efficiency. A study of Akarin Pallsawet [5] found that the general aspect of motivational factors and maintenance factors are related with effectiveness in work performance at Kao Industrial (Thailand) Co., Ltd. showed the general aspects of motivational factors and maintenance factors are related with effectiveness in work performance. Nipa Piboon [6] also studied the relationship between working motivation and working effectiveness at Office of the Basic Education Commission of Thailand staffs found that there was a relation between the two.

V. RECOMMENDATION

The management strategies need to be improved by using external motivation, concrete object, to motivate staff. The study of each work aspect shows only a medium level of staff that are motivated to work. The director should increase working motivation in every work aspect to produce a more effective and better staff in the organization. Readjust the management strategies by activating positive and working

behavior. Encourage the staff to work fully and direct them to their target goals by using working opportunity, working responsibility, and management policies. Using motivational force for example, awards, complements, and positions to motivate staff to work more effectively. The organization's goals should be reached due to increase the effectiveness in work performance.

The data analysis of working effectiveness in communication between co-worker and director found that the level of clarity and ease of work assignment were at the medium level. The director should clarify work assignments to the staff so they can meet objectives and goals. For example, arrange a relationship building event or practice normal conversation between the staff and directors. This will bring the organization closer together and the staff will be able to respond confidently to the director resulting in improved understanding of work assignments.

The comparison of working effectiveness in working flexibility by marriage status found that single status and marriage/ co- habitation status staffs had high working flexibility. Hence, the director should offer an opportunity for these employees to suggest their opinions on how to work effectively. Also, introduce a new way of working in order to achieve the performance goals and objectives. By these means single status and marriage/ co- habitation status staff should be able to adapt themselves in the ever-changing work environment. These efforts should bring a significant change to the efficiency of work to the Head Office of Krung Thai Public Company Limited.

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